

ANALYSIS OF DATA COLLECTION METHODS FOR AN IMAGE RECOGNITION PROGRAM WITH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. The majority of individuals have the ability to recognize faces quickly, interpreting expressions and emotions automatically. While humans are skilled in facial recognition, Computer Vision (CV) is advancing rapidly, sometimes outperforming humans in this area. Advances in CV and Machine Learning have led to efficient and accurate solutions surpassing human capabilities. The potential uses of this technology are broad, including applications in marketing and retail, driven by large datasets of faces with diverse features.

Keywords: Machine learning, computer vision, datasets, methods, image.

Аннотация. Большинство людей обладают способностью быстро распознавать лица, автоматически интерпретируя выражения и эмоции. В то время как люди обладают навыками распознавания лиц, компьютерное зрение быстро развивается, иногда опережая людей в этой области. Достижения в области компьютерного зрения и машинного обучения привели к созданию эффективных и точных решений, превосходящих возможности человека. Потенциальные области применения этой технологии широки, включая приложения в маркетинге и розничной торговле, основанные на больших наборах, данных о лицах с разнообразными чертами.

Ключевые слова: машинное обучение, компьютерное зрение, наборы данных, методы, изображение.

Annotatsiya. Aksariyat odamlar ifoda va his-tuyg'ularni avtomatik ravishda talqin qilish orqali yuzlarni tezda tanib olish qobiliyatiga ega. Odamlar yuzni aniqlash qobiliyatiga ega bo'lsa-da, kompyuter ko'rishi tez rivojlanmoqda, ba'zida bu sohada odamlardan oldinda. Kompyuter ko'rishi va mashinali o'qitishdagi yutuqlar inson imkoniyatlaridan yuqori bo'lgan samarali va aniq echimlarni yaratishga olib keldi. Ushbu texnologiyaning potentsial ilovalari keng, jumladan, marketing va chakana savdoda turli xil xususiyatlarga ega bo'lgan shaxslar haqidagi katta to'plamlarga asoslangan ilovalar.

Kalit so'zlar: mashinali o'qitish, kompyuter ko'rishi, ma'lumotlar to'plami, metodlar, tasvir.

Introduction

Facial recognition is a subset of image recognition that utilizes AI/ML models. Collecting data for facial recognition involves gathering face images to enhance FRSs by training them with annotated images of various individuals. The process of facial recognition software starts with gathering facial recognition data and processing images through Computer Vision. Images receive thorough digital screening to distinguish between a human face, a photo, a sculpture, or a poster. Machine learning is employed to detect patterns and similarities in the dataset. The ML algorithm recognizes facial features to identify a face in an image.

To achieve optimal performance, the facial recognition model needs training on diverse datasets. The software should be able to accurately read, identify, and recognize each unique face, including changes in facial contours caused by emotions. A solution is to gather photos of people from around the world with various angles, perspectives, and expressions to create a diverse database. This database, when uploaded to a centralized platform with clear annotations, allows for efficient quality control checks. Collecting high-quality images of different individuals is crucial for the software's effectiveness. Facial data collection is essential for the performance of facial recognition software, providing valuable details on facial features for accurate identification in dynamic environments using AI training data.

Machine learning algorithms have achieved high accuracy in face recognition systems. These algorithms consist of two components: data and the algorithm. However, machine learning-based face recognition techniques need many labeled samples, which are costly and time-consuming to acquire. The effectiveness of these techniques typically increases with better quality and quantity of data. Two ways to gather a significant amount of data include gathering face data from users and augmenting data from a limited dataset. Gathering a large number of face images is crucial for successful face recognition, and a method to enhance datasets by introducing variations in facial appearance was suggested. "One-to-many augmentation" methods can help overcome data collection challenges and expand datasets.

Data Collection Process

Careful selection of data augmentation techniques is crucial for training datasets, taking into account the dataset context and problem domain expertise. It is also beneficial to try out augmentation methods individually and assess any impact on model performance, possibly using a small dataset, model, and training. Despite being powerful, these techniques may require significant computational resources.

The basic steps included in face image data collection:

1. Comprehend the project's extent (identifying the types of faces to be scanned, the scale of the population it will cover, etc.).
2. Recruit participants
3. Take images based on the requirements of the project
4. Take images based on the requirements of the project

Figure 1. The basic steps in face image data collection

There are four main methods for data collecting as well as each accomplish different function for different programs.

1. Prepackaged/Public face image dataset. The datasets, produced by an external source, are available for instant use once bought. Occasionally, pre-made datasets are accessible free.
2. Face image data collection through crowdsourcing. The datasets, generated by a third party, are available for immediate use post-purchase.

Crowdsourcing involves collaborating with the public to collect new face image datasets. Internally, a company must create an online platform for the crowd to register, receive data collection tasks, and submit data for payment.

3. Automated face image data collection. Facial recognition systems can automate image data using machine learning by scraping or crawling online sources to collect data.

4. In-house face image data collection. This process consists of establishing a distinct project for gathering image data in order to build a facial recognition system. The team needs to buy cameras and lighting gear and recruit individuals to capture the images.

Choosing the appropriate method for your facial recognition project depends on various factors, including the project's size. For example, if the system is used in one country, pre-packaged or public datasets can be utilized. On the other hand, crowdsourcing is better for projects spanning multiple countries. Private projects may find in-house data collection beneficial, while public datasets are suitable for non-confidential or simpler projects. In-house data collection is costly and time-consuming, so using pre-packaged datasets or crowdsourcing may be better for projects with limited time and funds.

For an automated attendance program for schools universities or companies with a large number of employees, the best method is automated face image. In this way might be created link where every student or employee could leave his or her image for further data processing. By clicking on the link, the user gets to a site with a camera where it is indicated in which position to stand for how many seconds to fix the image. A collection of data is trained in advance with the learning machine so that participants leave the correct photos in good quality. This is the most cost-effective method, and taking into account time and money and labor.

The primary function of the machine learning (ML) pipeline is to automate ML and parameter tuning for analyzing data patterns. ML can identify relationships between observations and responses. Implementation of the ML pipeline in our proposed architecture must meet objectives like supporting distributed computing for scalability and providing tools for feature analysis and iterative ML algorithms.

1. Data Imputation: Filling in missing values in a dataset involves replacing them with an estimate and then analyzing the data set as if the filled values were observed.

2. Feature Selection: Automatically selecting relevant attributes in a data set is crucial for face recognition systems.

3. Dimension Reduction: To simplify face recognition while maintaining performance, irrelevant, redundant, or noisy features are typically excluded. This reduces the number of variables considered.

4. Data Balancing: Having a balanced training set helps improve recognition accuracy and fairness by ensuring an equal representation of features.

5. Discretization: Transforming continuous functions, models, and equations into discrete forms is the final step in the discretization process.

The primary bottleneck in these steps is the need for the model to make decisions based on a collective representation of large data sets using calculated

estimates. Pre-processing tasks involve intricate computations limited by the number of dimensions or features to consider. For instance, in facial recognition applications, higher dimensions result in more complex computations. Translating classical computational tasks into distributed computing tasks presents a major challenge in modeling. This additional step was not necessary in traditional methods. Accuracy and error rates when using distributed computing frameworks compared to classical methods are also areas of concern. Data pre-processing plays a crucial role in data mining as real-world data may be imperfectly gathered for various reasons, leading to issues like distorted images or measurement errors. It is important to address these big data challenges by leveraging existing research in the field.

Conclusion

Selecting the right approach for facial recognition project depends on a variety of factors, such as the project's size. On the other hand, crowdsourcing is more suitable for projects that cover multiple countries. Private projects may benefit from collecting data in-house, while public datasets are more appropriate for simpler or non-confidential projects. In-house data collection can be expensive and time-consuming, so using pre-packaged datasets or crowdsourcing may be ideal for projects with limited time and resources. For automated attendance systems in schools, universities, or companies with a large workforce, automated face image technology is the preferred method. This allows users to submit their images for data processing through a designated link, where they will be guided on how to pose and capture their image. The data collection process is trained in advance using machine learning to ensure participants provide quality photos. This approach is the most cost-effective considering time, money, and effort.

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